

Plethora of Education 4.0: Transforming Learners by Integrating Cyber Technology Into Teaching

Gideelyn S. Novabos

Abstract. The study scrutinized the strategies teachers employ to cope with the development of 21st-century skills to adapt to the demands of Education 4.0. This study used a phenomenological research design to determine the experiences and perceptions of the eight (8) participants. The themes on teachers' perception of integrating technology in the teaching-learning process were integrating emerging technologies, applying project-based and experiential learning, and emphasizing soft skills. Meanwhile, regarding teachers' strategies, the themes provided opportunities to be content creators fostered academic integrity and applied interactive learning platforms. Lastly, the themes from the values of their experiences were validating internet information, learning autonomy, and developing skills in digital literacy. Digital literacy skills are needed to operate various media platforms so that students can receive information ethically and adequately use them. It is necessary to improve the digital literacy skills of students and educators so that they show creativity and innovation in supporting digital learning. Teachers are no longer just disseminators of information but curators of digital resources, architects of experiential learning journeys, and nurturers of holistic skill sets. Moreover, the results provided comprehensive data for future research with similar scope.

KEY WORDS

1. education 4.0 2. communication and information technology 3. 21st century learning

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1. Introduction

The development of education in the world cannot be separated from the development of the industrial revolution because it indirectly changes the economic system, which affects the educational system. The Industrial Revolution began from the Industrial Revolution 1.0 and occurred in the 18th century through the invention of the steam engine, which allowed goods to be mass-produced. The Industrial Revolution of 2.0 occurred in the 19th and 20th centuries through electricity usage, which made production costs cheaper. The Industrial Revolution 3.0 occurred around the 1970s through the use of computers. Moreover, we are now in the industrial revolution 4.0. Similarly, Education 4.0, a period of great potential, can be defined as the integration of ICTs into educational settings to revolutionize instructional, pedagogical, and technological processes. This integration not only enhances operational processes but also paves the way for new learning and teaching methods, offering innovative solutions

to current and future societal challenges. It happened around the 2010s through engineering intelligence and the Internet of Things as the core of the movement and connectivity of humans and machines (Prasetyo Trisyanti, 2019). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2020 report of the United Nations (UN) Agenda 2030 underscores the global commitment to inclusive, equitable, and quality education for all (SDG4). This commitment is further reinforced by the promotion of sustained economic growth through optimized productivity and progressive use of technology. The SDGs envision robust economies and a diligent workforce that is Global Citizens (Bourn, 2018). The term 4.0 was originally initiated by the German government to promote computerization manufacturing in the implementation of the digital economy (Risdianto, 2019). Meanwhile, Education 4.0 is a common term used by scientists to define many ways to integrate cyber technology into the teaching-learning process. This is because sophisticated technological development can affect the way we think and act in our daily lives. In Indonesia, the system of education has extremely improved. It can be seen that the government has made several attempts to increase the quality of national education through the implementation of Education 4.0. The government has introduced ICT usage in classrooms and national exams to bring technology into the education space. Nonetheless, this practice remains limited to a cluster of schools. This is a new challenge to redefine the new Education 4.0 and identify intelligent people who are creative and innovative. Since it has become a digital society, it has created changes in the lifestyle of distance, time, and places. It connects all people globally with a wider vision and keeps updating faster. The development of media technology majors is almost all the activity today, including education. This will make their perspective of life change into more addicted to the machinery with more advancement

both in its function and programs (Pooworawan, 2019). Malaysia, as an emerging economy, intends to be prepared and equipped for Education 4.0. The drive towards this aim has been part of the country's Education Blueprint 2015-2025, the 2050 National Transformation (TN50) aspiration, and the Higher Education 4.0 policies (Rozana, 2019). Hussin (2018) pointed out that tertiary education in the country supports a flexible seating arrangement that is more supportive of both individual and collaborative workspaces. Alternative assessments are used to accommodate multiple learning styles, and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) and other online learning platforms are already utilized. Similarly, in the USA, data showed that the country had been leading foundational research in artificial intelligence (AI), cascading it down to research initiatives on strategic computing, big data, and brain research. Likewise, Canada supports Learning in the Digital Age, highlighting Digital and Media Literacy, which gives students the adaptive capabilities to be an active part in the global digital society (Brown-Martin, 2018). Penprase (2018) cited that the proliferation of new educational institutions and new curricula after the first two industrial revolutions enabled the technical and managerial capacity to implement the massive expansion of the economy and manufacturing that arose in the twentieth century. The most familiar exponential technology is the exponential increase in computer power and decreasing cost in storage, which obeys a geometric relation commonly known as Moore's Law. In the Philippines, Department of Education (DepEd) Secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones discussed public policy in education in the context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution during the 118th Founders' Day of Silliman University in Dumaguete City on August 25, 2019. Briones mentioned that with artificial intelligence, there is increasing access to education by breaking through language and physical barriers; there is so much

data available for 21st-century learners. She also cited that the challenge is to teach the learners how to analyze and make sense of the data that they are being flooded with. There is a need to develop the capacity not only for the learners but also for the teachers and for the institutions producing the teachers to discern what data is relevant (DepEd Press release, 2019). With the demands of rapid development, educators must be aware that education should make necessary adaptations to technological advancement. Various kinds of technology have been applied in the process of learning. Before, the teacher should teach by conservative methods like explaining in detail and taking a note in the book about all the teacher's explanations. But now, the use of technology development, such as computers, LCD projectors, and internet access, has made the process of learning more effective and efficient. Schools should prepare students for the future of work. Students should be capable and ethical in utilizing these new technological tools. They should also be critical, creative, self-directed, reflective, and decent citizens and leaders. This scenario calls for learning institutions to keep abreast of these latest trends and come up with new and responsive ways to enhance teaching and learning (Alda et al., 2020). With the advent of education reform, Education 4.0 presents both promising opportunities and formidable challenges; many high school teachers in Davao City encountered challenges in integrating a skillful, technologically driven learning environment. This demands a new set of skills and pedagogical approaches from educators to successfully build 21st-century skilled learners amidst the challenges. Some of the pressing challenges are that some students do not have equal access to technology and the internet, hindering equal learning opportunities. Indeed, schools started from the type of education 1.0, where everything is dedicated and learning is very limited; nowadays, the 4.0 level of learning is everywhere with the help of technology and with the latest use of gadgets. This growing need pushes teachers to thrive. My study highlights the integration of Education 4.0 in the curriculum and instruction under principle 2 of school-based management. My study will focus primarily on Sta. Maria Integrated School, Division of Davao City. It also investigates the strategies employed by teachers to cope with the development of 21st-century skills in order to adapt to the demands of Education 4.0. However, my research did not delve into specific technical aspects of Education 4.0, nor did it extensively cover the evaluation of the entire K-12 curriculum. Instead, it concentrated on broader themes of technological integration in the classrooms. Moreover, my study contributed to the existing body of knowledge by providing information about the intersection of curriculum and the challenges posed by Education 4.0. My research aims to shed light on the necessary educational reforms and policies required to equip the next generation with the skills and knowledge demanded by the rapidly changing global landscape. My study aimed to contribute to a well-informed and forward-looking educational landscape that prepares students for the challenges and opportunities of the future.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The goal of my study was to investigate the coping strategies employed by teachers with the development of 21st-century skills in order to adapt to the demands of Education 4.0. This is a vital subject in the education system, designed to equip students with the knowledge and skills necessary to understand and engage with society and the world around them. Specifically, my study aimed to draw significant information from the participants in terms of their personal experiences of their intervention practices and their coping mechanisms. Interventions have been implemented by the teachers, but their effectiveness is contingent on the

circumstances of the learners.

1.2. *Research Questions*—The primary research questions of this study were the following:

- (1) What challenges do teachers face in transforming learning by integrating cyber technology into teaching?
- (2) What coping strategies are used by teachers with the challenges of integrating the concept of Education 4.0 into the curriculum?
- (3) What values are drawn from the teachers' experience?

1.3. *Definition of Terms*—The following terms are operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Education 4.0 is a term often used to describe the latest phase of educational evolution that leverages advanced technology and innovative pedagogical approaches to transform traditional learning models. 21st-century learning involves developing a highly valuable skill set for the future. These skills are critical for the digital and evolving economy. Instead of specific subject knowledge, 21st-century skills are ways of thinking, working, and living. Transforming education- refers to a comprehensive and often systemic process of making significant changes

and improvements to the educational system to enhance learning outcomes, adaptability, and relevance in a rapidly changing world. This transformation encompasses various aspects of education, including curriculum, teaching methods, educational technologies, assessment practices, and the overall educational environment. Teaching strategies- refer to the systematic and planned approaches that educators use to facilitate learning and engage students in the educational process. These strategies encompass various instructional methods, techniques, and tactics designed to help students acquire knowledge, develop skills, and achieve specific learning objectives.

1.4. *Significant of the Study*—To explore the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings be addressed, the following persons or agencies may be the beneficiaries. Department of Education. The findings may offer evidence-based insights that can inform decisions related to curriculum design, instructional methods, and resource allocation. By understanding the impact of Education 4.0 on student learning and skill development, the department can make informed choices that align with educational goals. The study's findings may also guide the revision of curricula to ensure they are up-to-date and aligned with the skills needed in a technology-driven society. Principals. There is an underlying significance to the conduct of this study. For the school, findings would provide a basis for the teacher's training and policy development. The conduct of blended learning could

be examined to identify the current practices and, therefore, address the issues and challenges encountered by teachers. Teachers. The findings of the study would enable them to realize procedures of integrating Education 4.0 being the essential approach to preparing the learners for the 21st century. Informed results would provide teachers with practical procedures for integrating 21st-century skills and transversal competencies in their lesson facilitation. When the teachers clearly understand the concept of Education 4.0, they tend to explicitly implement the integration in the curriculum through teaching strategies and activities. The development of essential 21st-century skills and transversal competencies would be facilitated. Future researchers. This qualitative study provides insights on developing curriculum based on the concepts of education 4.0. As the findings con-

tribute to the existing knowledge on curriculum designing that is compliant with Education 4.0, the study could be a means to support further studies to be conducted using a quantitative approach. Hence, progressing the research focuses on curriculum development and education 4.0.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—My study is anchored on Becker’s Theory of Human Capital (1964), which posits that investments in education and training contribute to the development of human capital, enhancing individual productivity and overall economic growth. In the context of this study, the theory underscores the significance of K-12 education as an essential investment in the human capital of Filipino students. Another theory is the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989), which explores individuals’ acceptance and adoption of new technologies. This theory will aid in understanding how stakeholders, including teachers and students, perceive and embrace the integration of IR 4.0 technologies within the educational system. By identifying factors that influence the acceptance of emerging technologies, the study aims to ascertain the readiness of educators and students to incorporate digital tools into the learning process effectively. This study is also guided by the theory of technology dominance, which was a theoretical framework that seeks to understand the impact of technology on organizations and society. The theory proposes that technology can have a dominant influence on organizational behavior, decision-making, and performance. One of the key strengths of the theory of technology dominance is its ability to explain how technology can shape organizational behavior and decision-making. The theory suggests that the increasing dependence on technology can lead to organizations becoming more centralized, hierarchical, and bureaucratic. Additionally, the theory proposes that the increasing use of technology can lead to organizations becoming more data-driven, with decisions being based on data rather than intuition or experience. Globalization Theory, as

propounded by Giddens in 1990, examines the interconnectedness of societies in an increasingly globalized world. The internationalization efforts to facilitate cross-cultural exchange and elevate the overall quality of education in the Philippines, preparing graduates to navigate the challenges and opportunities of an interconnected global landscape.

Another support theory was the Constructivism Theory of Piaget (1972). Constructivism is a learning theory that emerged in the early twentieth century and is strongly influenced by Piaget’s cognitive schema theory, Dewey’s views on the educative value of experience, and Montessori’s perspective on student-centered education. Constructivist approaches to education, particularly social and critical constructivism, encourage active, student-centered learning that recognizes the constructed nature of knowledge and encourages the development of critical consciousness. According to constructivist thought, individuals make meaning by actively constructing knowledge through personal interaction with the environment, with each new experience interpreted in the context of the experience and all preceding knowledge and events. Moreover, the theory of technology dominance is a theoretical framework that seeks to understand the impact of technology on organizations and society. The theory proposes that technology can have a dominant influence on organizational behavior, decision-making, and performance. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. Based on the figure, there are three interconnected variables. These variables are the Challenges teachers face in transforming learning through the integration of cyber technology into teaching, the coping strategies used by teachers with the challenges of inte-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

grating the concept of Education 4.0 into the curriculum, and the Values derived from teachers' experience. Understanding and applying these theories is essential for practical instruction and successful curriculum development". These principles provide different frameworks teachers can use to adapt to students' diverse learning styles and academic needs.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitated the consequent design and implementation. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group's cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks the question, "What was the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "The goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the challenges of the floating teachers. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that was greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—

The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field. It established the background for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types, which were elaborated to give further insight into their significance in the section below. **Ontology.** This part of the research pertained to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2019), the reality was subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addressed the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the coping strategies used by teachers with the challenges of integrating the concept of Education 4.0 into the curriculum in the development of 21st-century skills in order to adapt to the demands of Education 4.0 were explored. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. I upheld the authenticity of the responses and prevented them from making personal biases as the study progressed.

Epistemology. This referred to the aware-

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology describes a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias,

ness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2019), stated that the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself and the participants on the epistemological assumption. He suggested that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider.' This study intended to gather information from the teachers' experiences about the coping strategies used by teachers with the challenges of integrating the concept of Education 4.0 into the curriculum in the development of 21st-century skills to adapt to the demands of Education 4.0. It was assumed that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. **Axiology** refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2019) averred that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggested that I openly discuss the values that shaped the narrative and include their interpretation in conjunction with the participants' interpretation. I ensured the dignity and value of every piece of information obtained from the participants. I understood the information gathered from the study to be personal and value-laden. Therefore, I preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted them in light of their interpretations. **Rhetoric.** This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher wrote in a literary, informal style using a personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions.

2019). In this study, the strategies employed by teachers to cope with the development of 21st-century skills and adapt to the demands of Education 4.0 were explored, particularly those of the teachers from Sta. Maria Integrated School, Cluster 12, Division of Davao City. My drive

as a researcher to know the deeper meaning of their experiences became the basis for doing qualitative research. It was considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underlie cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena.” By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge; this experience was a source of knowledge and shapes one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design, since it would focus on teachers’ perspective about Education 4.0. Creswell (2019) stressed that phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, I was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2020) also added that with roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology attempted to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, bracketing is a method I used as a researcher to document

of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research is that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2020).

By doing phenomenology, which concerns the “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 2020), I projected that the teachers’ subjective experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms were explored, and insights were drawn as a basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes.

According to Corbetta (2020), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provided in-depth methods that granted access to deep knowledge and explanations and helped grasp the subjects’ perspective. Creswell (2019) also claimed that interviews were primarily used in qualitative research. They occurred when researchers asked one or more participants general, open-ended questions and recorded their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were also useful for following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to further investigate their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 2020). Based on Quad’s (2020) statements, the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after the interview. Interviews were

beneficial for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. As a researcher, I collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via long interviews. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts.

Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, a textural description of what was experienced, and a structural description of how it was experienced. I incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. I required a solid grounding in the philosophical guide-

2.4. Research Participants—The participants of this study were the eight teachers of Sta. Maria Integrated School, Cluster 12, Division of Davao City. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: they must have been in their present position for at least five years,

regardless of their age, sex, and marital status; they must have been teaching for at least

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. I needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participants in this field. Ethical considerations were specified as one of the most important parts of the research. I needed to adhere to promoting the

lines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. I needed to bracket my own experiences and observations, which was difficult. I also needed to decide how and when to incorporate my observations into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore the coping strategies used by teachers to address the challenges of integrating the concept of Education 4.0 into the curriculum and developing 21st-century skills to adapt to the demands of Education 4.0, I intended to employ phenomenology as a qualitative method.

five years, regardless of their age, sex, and marital status; and they must have at least a very satisfactory rating in IPCRF. I utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings were authentic (Marshall, 1996).

research aims, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and error prevention. Social Value. The research was essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was explicitly conducted among teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more

programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushed my interest was the development of 21st-century skills to adapt to the demands of Education 4.0. **Informed Consent.** In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2020), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary and based on the understanding of adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants were lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2020). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating. **Vulnerability of Research Participants.** The study participants could answer the research instrument because they were all professional teachers in public schools. Thus, I assured them that as a researcher, I could easily be reached through the contact number and addressed in case of any clarifications or questions regarding the study. **Risks, Benefits, and Safety.** The respondents were recruited free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Further-

more, in the event that respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered conveniently. The dominant concern of this study is the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk.

This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. **Privacy and Confidentiality of Information.** This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so that there was no conflict of interest among the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way were avoided. **Justice.** The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to give their full honesty in answering the survey questions, and any communication concerning the research was done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they would benefit first from the study results. **Transparency.** The study's results were accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information was available and was placed in CDs or other storage devices they could request the researcher to provide. In addition, by learning from the study results, participants were

aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process. They could be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them.

I reserved the right to use pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. I ensured that I possessed the necessary qualifications to conduct the study. I completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree, and I was qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study reached its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. I strived to ensure that the study could be completed successfully in the specified time and that he or she was equipped with

the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving suggestions and recommendations for improving the study. Also, I ensured that I had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. I showed respect for the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, I expressed great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. I respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said his or her way. I also used quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, I ensured honesty when working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation or

distortion of data or results was included or that no purposefully erroneous conclusions were put forward.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—I was responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, the researcher took up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. I conducted interviews with the participants and guided them in the process. I interpreted ideas and responded based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. I implemented the qualitative method correctly. To do so, I assessed myself and sought help from the research adviser and other research professionals. These helped me demonstrate

competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. I ensured different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. The records I have made were secured adequately as they contained sensitive information and were relevant to the research.

However, when the data were being collected, my primary responsibility was safeguarding participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding were clearly articulated to participants and were approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research began. Analyst of data. I saw the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. I ensured that the findings accurately re-

flected the participants' experiences and that their voices were heard. I organized and presented the data. I presented the problem and the related literature and studies that supported it. The study's findings were presented, too, by research question, stating the results for each one using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gave future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

2.7. Data Collection—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. In September 2023, I asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. I sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument explaining the study's objectives and the participants' identification. I waited for the SDS's response before conducting it. I asked permission from the school heads. In the same month, after securing the SDS's approval, I sent letters to the principals explaining the study to be conducted in their schools.

interview using the interview questionnaire. I took the participants' profiles, took notes, and recorded conversations using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. I carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. In December 2023, I transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, I translated it to English. Data Coding and Thematizing. In January 2024, after the transcription, the data were categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data were compared and contrasted. I then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants. Additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

Obtaining consent from the participants. In September 2023, I still asked permission from the participants. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. In September 2023, I conducted an in-depth

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. I analyzed the participants' answers from the interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2019), themes in qual-

itative research were similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database.

Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis. I immersed myself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting

any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for essential features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method; it was also an analytic process, so codes captured both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. I coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. I ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. I reflected

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The framework analysis of this research was flexible, allowing me to either collect all the data and then analyze it or conduct data analysis during the collection process. The gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted by key issues and themes in the analysis stage. This involved a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 2019). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher became familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes) and gained an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher became immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, I became aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and noted them. Due to the sheer volume of data collected in qualitative research, I could not review all of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set was utilized. The selection depended on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, a mix of meth-

on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: I prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing up. This involved weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it about existing literature. I ensured that the perspectives of teachers were presented comprehensively.

ods was used. Interviews, documents, observations. The second stage, identifying a thematic framework, occurs after familiarization, when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues that had arisen from a priori themes were issues; however, at this stage, I allowed the data to dictate the themes and issues. I used the notes taken during the familiarization stage to achieve this end. The key issues, concepts, and themes expressed by the participants now formed the basis of a thematic framework used to filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means identifying portions or sections of the data that corresponded to a particular theme. This process was applied to all the textual data that had been gathered (e.g., transcripts of interviews). For convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used to index references and annotate them in the margin beside the text. Qualitative data analysis tools were ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping and interpretation, involved the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis provided a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding me in my interpretation of the data set. At this

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

point, I was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis, which were defining concepts, mapping the range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies.

Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations reflected the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echoed the true attitudes, beliefs, and values of the participants.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability were relatively foreign to qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substituted data trustworthiness, which consisted of credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2020). Credibility involved establishing that the research findings were credible or believable from the participants’ perspectives. Observing the attributes of prolonged engagement is where credibility contributed to a belief in the trustworthiness of data. To address the credibility issue, I interviewed as many research participants as

possible or up to the point of saturation. Meanwhile, transferability was the degree to which the findings were generalized or transferred to other contexts. In this, I did a thorough job of describing the research context and assumptions that were relevant. On the other hand, dependability was the consistency and repeatability of the research. I ensured that the study’s findings were evaluated by the participants and scrutinized by an external reviewer. Lastly, conformability was the degree to which other researchers could confirm or corroborate findings. I documented the procedures and rechecked the data during the entire research process. I also made sure that the findings were true and correct.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents and discusses the study's results with reference to its aim. It also discusses the themes that emerged from the data gathered. The results present the description and background of the participants who were assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities.

*3.1. Challenges Teachers Face in Transforming Learning through the Integration of Cyber Technology into Teaching—*The emergence of Education 4.0 signals a transformative shift in the teaching-learning process. It represents the integration of cutting-edge technologies and innovative pedagogical approaches to create a dynamic and student-centric learning environment. Teachers play a pivotal role in this revolution, for they have navigated the exciting terrain of digital advancements and adapted their teaching methods to meet the needs of 21st-century learners. This section delves into how teachers embrace Education 4.0 in integrating cyber technology into the teaching-learning process. The responses of the teachers were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on what came from informants' accounts and reflections. *Integrating Emerging Technologies.* According to the participants, emerging technologies have the potential to significantly improve teaching and learning methods since they allow for more individualized learning and teaching experiences. Hence, they are practicing these promising technologies inside their classrooms. For them, teachers who embrace emerging technologies in the classroom exhibit a profound commitment to innovative pedagogy. The participants' responses corroborate with Ehlers (2020) that Education 4.0 thrives on cutting-edge technologies such as artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and augmented reality. Integrate these technologies into the curriculum to create immersive and engaging learning experiences. For instance, virtual field trips, interactive simulations, and AI-powered tutoring systems can enhance students' understanding and retention of complex concepts. Meanwhile, Learning and Teaching Online (2021) has accelerated the development of a range of teaching practices that involve emerging technologies such as streaming of live lessons, accessing recorded lessons, collaborative learning, networked professional learning, supporting learning through social media, learning in immersive virtual environments, hybrid learning, support to parents/parents in a learning support role, asynchronous learning and teaching, game-based learning, mobile learning and open education resources. Many of these technologies have been emerging for several years. Many continue to evolve at pace and will be in a state of continuous emergence. Emerging Technologies play a vast role in the educational process. The application of emerging technologies in education is changing learners' experiences inside and beyond the classrooms. Diane and Steven (2020) stated that there is an evolving relationship between education and technology, and the evolving pedagogies have also taken advantage of newly designed or emerging technologies. Indeed, one of the most important aspects of technology in education is its ability to level the field of opportunity for students. It can be a powerful tool for transforming learning; it can help affirm and advance relationships between educators and students, reinvent the approaches to learning and collaboration, shrink long-standing equity and accessibility gaps, and adapt learning experiences to meet the needs of all learners.

3.1.1. Applying Project-Based and Experiential Learning—

For the participants, Education 4.0 is not merely about the use of technologies but also about placing a strong emphasis on personalized and adaptive learning experiences. It recognizes that every student is unique, with distinct learning styles, preferences, and paces of comprehension. It also promotes learners that can survive in the midst of problems and challenges. For them, a project-based and experiential learning approach is best in providing opportunities for students to acquire skills useful in their future workplace. The participants' responses verify the findings of Goodman (2020) that the project-based and experiential approach is innovative because of its emphasis on cooperative learning. Additionally, students create tangible results to represent what they have learned. Students use technology and inquiry to respond to complex issues, problems, or challenges. Activities match the real-world tasks of professionals in practice rather than classroom-based tasks as nearly as possible. This encourages interdis-

3.1.2. Emphasizing Soft Skills—Personality characteristics are regularly called soft skills in contrast to cognitive abilities and technical knowledge, often called hard skills (Heckman Kautz, 2021). In line with this, the participants believed that teachers also need to emphasize soft skills to equip students with the resilience to navigate evolving technologies, diverse learning environments, and dynamic career landscapes. The ability to embrace change becomes a cornerstone for success in Education 4.0. Education 4.0 recognizes that soft skills, such as communication, adaptability, and emotional intelligence, are essential for success in the digital age. Infuse the curriculum with opportunities for students to develop these skills through group discussions, presentations, teamwork, and interpersonal interactions.

These skills complement technological proficiency and make students well-rounded (Smith Johnson, 2020). Armstrong, S. (2012). Arm-

ciplinary perspectives and enables learners to play diverse roles and build expertise that is applicable beyond a single well-defined. Lastly, it allows a range and diversity of outcomes open to multiple solutions rather than a single correct response obtained by applying predefined rules and procedures. While a project may address a specific problem, it can also focus on areas that are not problems. A key characteristic of project-based and experiential learning is that it does not focus on learning about something. It focuses on doing something. It is action-oriented. In the 21st Century, where Education 4.0 is established, in a fast-changing, complex, and often tricky world of endless challenges and accelerating crises people have to increasingly deal with what many are calling 'wicked problems,' e.g. – That is, complex problems without any obvious, simple solutions requiring greater collaboration and the linking of different areas or disciplines of knowledge (Armstrong, 2020).

strong, S. (2012). Natural learning in higher education, Educational systems must adapt to give students the skills necessary to build a more just and productive world for society. Schools must provide the learning of complex skills, such as technology design and resource management, and soft skills, such as communication, empathy, and social awareness, allowing students to shape inclusive and equitable societies (WEF, 2020). Such skills are essential to enable people to progress in a more complex, interconnected and rapidly changing world (OECD, 2019). Students who are better prepared for the future will be agents of change, able to influence and understand other people's intentions and feelings positively and to foresee the short—and long-term consequences of problems that affect society (OECD, 2018). Therefore, according to Schleicher (2021), teachers must use digital technologies in teaching and understand the accelerated development of diverse knowledge

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on What are the Challenges Teachers Face in Transforming Learning through the Integration of Cyber Technology into Teaching fields. The figure shows the emerging themes on the teacher’s perception of integrating technology in the teaching-learning process. The themes were integrating emerging technologies, applying project-based and experiential learning, and emphasizing soft skills. These themes implied that teachers are pivotal in shaping the next generation, not just as knowledgeable individuals but as adaptable, collaborative, and emotionally intelligent leaders. Educators contribute to the holistic development of students, preparing them to thrive in a world that requires more than just academic proficiency — it demands the capabilities of agile, empathetic, and innovative individuals. In nurturing these holistic skills, teachers become architects of a brighter and more resilient future.

3.2. *Coping Strategies Used by the Teachers with the Challenges of Integrating the Concept of Education 4.0 into the Curriculum*—The emergence of Education 4.0 marks a significant shift in the way we approach teaching and learning, harnessing the power of technology and connectivity to create a more dynamic and personalized educational experience. As schools and educational institutions strive to adapt to

this new era, integrating the principles of Education 4.0 into the curriculum becomes essential (Smith Johnson, 2020). This section delves into teachers’ strategies in coping with the challenges of integrating the concept of Education 4.0 into the curriculum. The responses of the teachers were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on what came from informants’ accounts and reflections.

3.2.1. *Providing opportunities to be content creators—*

According to the participants, one good news for educators, like them, who are constantly looking to find and promote more opportunities to have students as creators, not consumers, is that there are plenty of creativity tools for students that will work great in order to achieve this goal, thanks to the technologies brought by Education 4.0. The participants believed that these creation tools can promote the building of valuable skills as well as increase opportunities for students to learn digital citizenship along the way. They can gain experience producing work for a wider audience than just their teacher while also learning to be cognizant of their responsibilities to a more authentic audience. Education 4.0 signifies a departure from traditional teaching methods, emphasizing the cultivation of critical thinking, creativity, and digital literacy. As noted by Anderson and Dron (2011), this shift involves moving from the "sage on the stage" model to a more collaborative and participatory "guide on the side" approach. In this context, providing students with opportunities to create content becomes instrumental in preparing them for the challenges of the modern, interconnected world. Kreiness

3.2.2. *Fostering academic integrity*—participants recognize their duty to uphold academic integrity and foster ethical behavior in the classrooms. Nevertheless, the advent of artificial intelligence (AI) in Education 4.0 introduces complexities in addressing these concerns and guaranteeing responsible and ethical usage of AI by students. Consequently, it becomes crucial to establish explicit policies governing the use of AI in academic tasks, aimed at maintaining the highest standards of academic integrity. According to the participants, gaining expertise in citation requires practical application. Offering students hands-on training in different citation styles guarantees their proficiency in the norms of academic writing. This training

(2023) concurs that finding ways to have students as school content creators does not simply satisfy that dream. It builds valuable life and career skills that will likely serve them well. Furthermore, as any good educator should know, the top-most level of higher-order thinking in Bloom's Taxonomy is creating. Having students as content creators allows them to demonstrate their learning in ways that contribute to better mastery of content and standards. Furthermore, for Bush (2021), a future-ready educator encourages students as creators to promote student engagement and agency in learning and to develop adaptive skills and habits of mind. Schools, libraries, and classrooms have traditionally been a place to consume information and ideas. Empowering students as creators means educators shift their professional thinking, instruction, and instructional program to enable authentic opportunities for students to individually and collaboratively tinker, build, inquire, design, create, and iterate. This is accomplished by designing and delivering instruction that provides opportunities for students to own their learning and demonstrate that learning through creativity, collaboration, and design (Bush, 2021).

should also include the citation of AI-generated content, emphasizing that these tools are beneficial aids but not replacements for independent thought. Moreover, the participants claimed that paraphrasing is as important as proper citation. Paraphrasing in academic writing is an effective way to restate, condense, or clarify another author's ideas while also providing credibility to their own argument or analysis. While successful paraphrasing is essential for strong academic writing, unsuccessful paraphrasing can result in unintentional plagiarism. The responses from the participants align with the views presented by Perkins (2023) regarding AI language models as tools that can assist in the writing processes. According to his perspective, the use of generated

content in academic writing can be deemed acceptable and non-plagiaristic if it is critically assessed, rephrased, and appropriately cited. Advocates for this stance assert that AI language models serve as valuable resources for inspiring ideas, examining diverse viewpoints, and overcoming writer's block. Perkins emphasizes that the writer is responsible for evaluating and transforming the generated content into original work. In a parallel vein, Gavilán et al. (2022) recognized the emphasis on academic integrity and ethical writing practices, underscoring the significance of accurate citation and attribution. In the context of academic writing involving AI language tools, it is imperative to recognize their role as tools or sources of assistance and to cite them when integrating generated content

3.2.3. Application of interactive learning platforms—Digitization has widened the scope for teachers, and they no longer have to stick to traditional, defined, restricted curricula and methods of teaching. The devices and technology used in interactive learning will optimize time spent on teaching and learning and are also environment-friendly. For the participants, utilizing interactive online platforms and tools that support collaborative and interactive learning. Platforms like Google Classroom, Moodle, or other Learning Management Systems (LMS) can facilitate communication, assignment submission, and resource sharing. The responses of the participants verify the assertion of Gregory (2023) that interactive learning can take place in many ways and through various tools, including but not limited to interactive displays, online platforms, interactive games, or group activities. These forms of learning are particularly effective at fostering the five critical skills for the digital classroom. In the past, learning intensely focused on memorizing facts and figures. Conversely, modern pedagogical strategies, recognizing the importance of these necessary skills

appropriately. While this perspective is widely accepted by many academic institutions, it remains crucial to scrutinize the specific regulations and citation conventions set forth by individual institutions or educational communities. Adhering to the rules and standards established by the academic community is essential, as institutional policies may vary. Alneyadi and Wardat (2023) concur that it is essential to recognize the limitations of these technologies. They are not infallible and should be employed alongside human skill and judgment. Furthermore, ethical considerations, transparency, and safeguarding student privacy must be diligently addressed when integrating AI technologies in educational settings.

in the digital classroom, have shifted towards more meaningful learning experiences. In addition, one must also remember that interactive learning platforms, when designed and implemented correctly, can cater to various learning styles and makes it easier for all students to feel comfortable in the classroom. Education 4.0, characterized by the integration of cutting-edge technologies into the educational landscape, has witnessed a profound transformation in teaching and learning methodologies. Central to this evolution is the widespread adoption of interactive learning platforms. These platforms, exemplified by tools like Google Classroom, Moodle, and Learning Management Systems (LMS), are pivotal in shaping a dynamic, personalized, and collaborative educational experience. Incorporating multimedia elements within these platforms, such as videos, interactive quizzes, and simulations, significantly enhances student engagement (Khan, 2019). These dynamic and visually stimulating resources captivate students' attention, making learning more enjoyable and effective. The figure above shows the emerging themes of teachers' strategies in coping with the

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on Coping Strategies used by the Teachers with the Challenges of Integrating the Concept of Education 4.0 into the Curriculum

challenges of integrating the concept of Education 4.0 into the curriculum. The themes provided opportunities to be content creators, fostered academic integrity, and allowed the application of interactive learning platforms. These themes implied that teachers in Education 4.0 must encourage critical thinking and problem-solving skills as students analyze information, synthesize ideas, and present their understanding in innovative ways. These skills are essential for success in the dynamic and complex challenges of the 21st century.

3.3. Values derived from the Teachers' Experience—This section presents the educational management insights of the participants. Their

responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on what came from informants' accounts and reflections.

3.3.1. Validating Internet Information—In the digital age, where information is readily accessible at the fingertips, the ability to discern credible and reliable sources has become a crucial skill. As students navigate the vast of information on the internet, teachers must emphasize the importance of validating information. The skills demanded of students are changing. So, they need to be open to change and adaptable. They need problem-solving skills, primarily virtual communication, managing big data, lead-

ing, and using technology effectively. One of the most critical skills demanded from students is questioning. Now, teachers need students who question and criticize information in Education 4.0 instead of downloading it without questioning, as in Education 1.0 (Himmeloglu et.al., 2019). According to Krahenbuhl (2020), Whether a person is a journalist, researcher, writer, or someone in the professional field, it is essential to know how to identify accurate information and use it accu-

rately; that's the real challenge in the 21st century. In an era characterized by the proliferation of information, the Internet is an unparalleled repository of knowledge and resources. With just a few clicks, we access a wealth of information spanning various subjects. However, in this vast ocean of data, the critical skill of analyzing downloaded information from the Internet has emerged as an indispensable tool for individuals seeking accurate, reliable, and valuable knowledge. This essay delves into the significance of this skill and how it empowers individuals to navigate the digital landscape effectively. Analyzing downloaded information from the In-

ternet is vital for ensuring the authenticity and reliability of the data we consume. The Internet is a treasure trove of accurate information and a breeding ground for misinformation, bias, and fake news. In a world where information spreads at lightning speed, it is incumbent upon individuals to critically assess the credibility of sources, cross-reference information, and distinguish fact from fiction. By developing the skill of discernment, users can safeguard themselves from falling victim to the pitfalls of misinformation, which can have profound consequences on personal decisions, societal perceptions, and even public policies (Himmetoglu et.al., 2019).

3.3.2. Learning Autonomy—Teachers should empower students to take ownership of their education, this will not only develop intrinsic motivation but also lay the groundwork for lifelong success. The participants believe that when students feel a sense of ownership, they are more likely to be engaged, enthusiastic, and driven by a genuine desire to understand and succeed- the recipes that Education 4.0 demands. The responses of the participants validate the findings of Gueye (2023) that the most important qualification of Education 4.0 demands from students is self-study skill, which includes starting to do something on their own and finishing it on their own. Along with that, students need to have skills such as working collaboratively and managing time effectively. In the context of Education 4.0, self-study is a transformative skill that transcends the passive consumption of information. It embodies the spirit of proactive learning, enabling stu-

dents to take the reins of their education and steer their intellectual growth. Self-study is characterized by the initiative to embark on a journey of discovery fueled by curiosity and a thirst for knowledge. It empowers students to identify learning gaps, set goals, and craft personalized learning paths tailored to their strengths and weaknesses. In a world inundated with information, the ability to discern relevant and reliable sources becomes a cornerstone of self-study, allowing students to confidently navigate the digital sea. Moreover, the true essence of self-study extends beyond the beginning of a task—it is about perseverance and determination to see it through to completion.

The tenacity to overcome obstacles, adapt strategies, and persist even in the face of challenges is emblematic of this qualification. Self-study nurtures resilience, fostering a growth mindset that instills the belief that setbacks are stepping stones toward mastery (Gueye, 2023).

3.3.3. They are developing Skills in Digital Literacy—The participants believe that students should have at least information literacy at the primary level. Interpreting and analyzing knowledge are crucial skills for students. The

most important things are interpreting, understanding, and comprehending knowledge. Otherwise, raw data are no longer helpful. Students should know how to reach knowledge very well. Computer literacy equips individuals with the

knowledge and skills necessary to navigate the vast and ever-evolving digital landscape. The responses of the participants verify the notion of Raj (2023) that in a rapidly changing world, computer literacy is an essential foundation for lifelong learning. It allows individuals to adapt to emerging technologies and continually upgrade their skills. With access to online courses, educational resources, and interactive platforms, computer literacy empowers individuals to pursue self-directed learning. It opens up opportunities for personal growth, acquiring new knowledge, and staying informed in a fast-paced digital society. Computer literacy fuels creativity by providing individuals with the tools to express their ideas and bring them to life.

Through digital media creation, graphic design, coding, and multimedia production, individuals can leverage computer literacy to unleash their creative potential. Computer literacy enables individuals to produce digital content, develop websites, design compelling visuals, and engage in digital storytelling. It fosters innovation, allowing individuals to contribute to the ever-expanding digital landscape (Raj,

2023). According to Mustofa, et al. (2023) there are several principles underlying the development of digital literacy. First, digital competence includes abilities, ideas, methods, and behaviors; second, digital use involves using digital competence in a specific context; and third, digital transformation means creativity and innovation are required in a digital world. Digital literacy is critical to instill from an early age in order to be able to understand information critically, analytically, and reflectively. The figure shows the emerging themes of the educational management insights drawn from the teachers' experiences. The themes were validating internet information, learning autonomy, and developing skills in digital literacy. These themes implied that learning using digital technology needs to be considered in the readiness of educators and students. Digital literacy skills are needed to operate various media platforms so that students can receive information ethically and adequately use them. It is necessary to improve the digital literacy skills of students and educators so that they show creativity and innovation in supporting digital learning.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on its findings. Future directions in the participants' experiences were also discussed here.

4.1. Findings—The study presents the key findings and emphasizes the significant function of teachers in responding to the challenges in Education 4.0 by supporting the acquisition of effective 21st-century skills. This entails the use of technologies that are new to the classroom, the use of project and experiential-based learning, and a focus on soft skills, all of which are hallmarks of a movement towards a new education system. Teachers are moving from the position where they passively educate their students to become guides and tutors as to how to navigate through this world of Information

Technology. They are emerging as designers of student and content portfolios and builders of learning experiences that translate between the academic and the real world. This transition requires constant professional development and the building of virtual classrooms to equip teachers with the preparation necessary to navigate students through it all. In this new mode of education, teachers cultivate these valuable assets for the learners in order to produce citizens who are flexible and creative and who can solve multifaceted problems in society today. This way, through teaching these skills, educators play an

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on the Values drawn from the Teachers' Experience

essential part in the students' upbringing as not only rational and erudite individuals but also emotionally literate and socially mindful.

To be able to effectively tackle the inherent difficulties of Education 4.0, teachers are incorporating tactics where learners are joining forums, writing blog posts, carrying out research, and using gadgets to avoid plagiarism and engage in participative learning. These strategies foster advanced skills in the problem-solving process and analysis of pertinent information in order to create new meaningful ideas and repre-

sentations. This approach promotes work, teamwork, and collaboration, fosters student learning, and improves social media awareness and technical skills, thus addressing the academic and job preparedness of students for future education and careers. Here, teachers do not only provide students with knowledge, but they play an essential role in making their students active participants in the learning process and enabling them to achieve success in today's increasingly competitive world.

4.2. Implications—The goal of this study was to investigate the coping strategies used by teachers with the challenges of integrating the concept of Education 4.0 into the curriculum in the development of 21st-century skills in order to adapt to the demands of Education 4.0. The emerging themes on the challenges teachers face in transforming learning through the integration of cyber technology into the teaching process were integrating emerging technologies, applying project-based and experiential

learning, and emphasizing soft skills. These themes implied that teachers are pivotal in shaping the next generation, not just as knowledgeable individuals but as adaptable, collaborative, and emotionally intelligent leaders. Educators contribute to the holistic development of students, preparing them to thrive in a world that requires more than just academic proficiency — it demands the capabilities of agile, empathetic, and innovative individuals. In nurturing these holistic skills, teachers become architects

of a brighter and more resilient future. The integration of emerging technologies into the teaching-learning process heralds a paradigm shift in education. Teachers are now not just conveyors of information but facilitators of digital literacy and technological fluency. The implications of this theme are vast, extending from the need for educators to continually upskill themselves to the imperative of creating digitally immersive learning environments. Project-based and experiential learning have emerged as potent tools in Education 4.0, bridging the gap between theory and practice. The implications of this theme transcend traditional classroom boundaries, requiring teachers to become orchestrators of hands-on, real-world learning experiences. Meanwhile, the emphasis on soft skills recognizes the need for a holistic approach to education. Beyond academic prowess, teachers were now tasked with fostering the development of essential skills such as communication, collaboration, critical thinking, and adaptability.

The convergence of these themes creates a tapestry that redefines the role of teachers in Education 4.0. Teachers are no longer just disseminators of information; they are curators of digital resources, architects of experiential learning journeys, and nurturers of holistic skill sets. Moreover, teachers' strategies for coping with the challenges of integrating Education 4.0 into the curriculum included providing opportunities to be content creators, fostering academic integrity, and applying interactive learning platforms. These themes implied that teachers in Education 4.0 must encourage critical thinking and problem-solving skills as students analyze information, synthesize ideas, and present their understanding in innovative ways. These skills are essential for success in the dynamic and

complex challenges of the 21st century. Teachers evolve from traditional roles to become facilitators and guides. They empower students to be content creators, fostering a collaborative and supportive learning environment rather than a one-way transfer of knowledge. The application of interactive learning platforms cultivates digital literacy and technological competence. Students become adept at navigating digital tools, collaborating online, and utilizing technology for educational and professional purposes. Further, students equipped with these skills are better prepared for the demands of higher education, the workforce, and lifelong learning. Lastly, the values drawn from the teachers' experience themes were validating internet information, learning autonomy, and developing skills in digital literacy. These themes implied that learning using digital technology needs to be considered in the readiness of educators and students. Digital literacy skills are needed in order to operate various forms of media platforms so that students can receive information properly and ethically use them. It is necessary to improve the digital literacy skills of

students and educators so that they show creativity and innovation in supporting digital learning. In addition, the themes' implications include the cultivation of critical thinking, resilience against misinformation, informed decision-making, ownership of learning, personalized learning paths, the cultivation of lifelong learners, preparation for the future workforce, effective communication in digital spaces, and ethical digital citizenship. Together, these aspects contribute to shaping well-rounded and adaptable individuals capable of thriving in the dynamic educational and professional landscape of Education 4.0.

4.3. Future Directions—Data obtained had future directions for various stakeholders in education including policymakers, adminis-

trators, and teachers. The future directions of this study were as follows: Policymakers may need to continually develop and update policies

that support the integration of Education 4.0. These policies should address issues such as digital infrastructure, teacher training, and the equitable distribution of technological resources. School Principals may prioritize ongoing professional development for teachers, ensuring they are well-versed in the latest educational technologies and teaching methodologies. This may involve workshops, seminars, and partnerships with educational technology experts. They may also allocate resources effectively to support the integration of technology in classrooms. Teachers may adopt student-centric teaching approaches that leverage technology to cater to diverse learning styles. They may use personalized learning plans and adaptive technologies to meet individual student needs.

They may also embrace a mindset of continuous learning and adaptability. They may attend regular training sessions, workshops, and online courses to stay updated on the latest educational technologies and teaching strategies. Moreover, future researchers may conduct in-depth research to assess the long-term impact of Education 4.0 on student outcomes, teacher effectiveness, and overall educational systems. They may evaluate different implementation models to identify best practices. These recommended studies will yield advantageous findings and implications tailored to the organization and hierarchical context of the education sector.

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